

The Crossing Number of $K_{1,5,n}$

Hanfei Mei

(Department of Mathematics, Hunan University of Arts and Science, Changde 415000, P.R.China)

E-mail: mhfm@21cn.com

Yuanqiu Huang

(Department of Mathematics, Hunan Normal University, Changsha 410081, P.R.China)

E-mail: hyqq@public.cs.hn.cn

Abstract: In this paper, we determine the crossing number of the complete tripartite graph $K_{1,5,n}$ for any integer $n \geq 1$, related with Smarandache 2-manifolds on spheres.

Key Words: Good drawings, complete tripartite graphs, crossing number.

AMS(2000) : O5C10

§1. Introduction

The *crossing number* $cr(G)$ of a graph G is the smallest crossing number among all drawings of G in the plane. It is well known that the crossing number of graph is attained only in good drawings of the graph related with *map geometries*, i.e., *Smarandache 2-manifolds* (see [8] for details), which are those drawings where no edges cross itself, no adjacent edges cross each other, no two edges intersect more than once, and no three edges intersect in a common point. Let ϕ be a good drawing of the graph G , we denote the number of crossings in this drawing of G by $cr_\phi(G)$.

The investigation on the crossing number of a graph is a classical and however very difficult problem (for example, see [3]). Garey and Johnson [4] have proved that the problem to determine the crossing number of a graph is NP-complete. Because of its difficulty, presently we only know the crossing number of some classes of special graphs, for example: the complete graphs with small number of vertices ([15]), the complete bipartite graph of less number of vertices in one bipartite partition ([7],[15]), certain generalized Peterson graphs ([12]), and some Cartesian product graphs of two circuits([2],[11]-[14]), of path and stars ([9]).

The crossing numbers of complete bipartite graphs $K_{m,n}$ were computed by D.J.Kleitman [7], for the case $m \leq 6$. He proved that

$$cr(K_{m,n}) = Z(m, n), \text{ if } m \leq 6, \text{ where } Z(m, n) = \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \rfloor \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor.$$

On the crossing number of the complete tripartite graphs, as far as the authors know, there

¹Received June 6, 2007. Accepted July 18, 2007

²Supported by The NNSF and Program for New Century Excellent Talents in University of China

only are the following two results: Kouhei Asano [1] proved that

$$cr(K_{1,3,n}) = Z(4, n) + \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor, \text{ and } cr(K_{2,3,n}) = Z(5, n) + n;$$

and Huang [5] recently proves that $cr(K_{1,4,n}) = n(n-1)$.

In this paper, using Kleitman's theorem, we determine the crossing number of complete tripartite graph $K_{1,5,n}$ for any integer $n \geq 1$. The main result of this paper is the following theorem.

Theorem 1 (the main result) *For any integer $n \geq 1$,*

$$cr(K_{1,5,n}) = Z(6, n) + 4\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$$

We now explain some notations. Let G be a graph with vertex set V and edge set E . If $A \subseteq E$ (or $A \subseteq V$), we use $G\langle A \rangle$ to denote the subgraph of G induced by A ; if G is known from the context, we simply write $\langle A \rangle$ instead of $G\langle A \rangle$. For two mutually disjoint subsets X and Y of V , we use E_{XY} to denote all the edges of G incident with a vertex in X and a vertex in Y . For a vertex v , E_v denotes all the edges of G incident with v .

Let A and B be two sets of edges of a graph G . If ϕ is a good drawing of G , we denote $cr_\phi(A, B)$ by the number of all crossings whose two crossed edges are respectively in A and in B . Especially, $cr_\phi(A, A)$ will be denoted by $cr_\phi(A)$. If G has the edge set E , the two signs $cr_\phi(G)$ and $cr_\phi(E)$ are essential the same.

The following formulas, which can be shown easily, are usually used in the proofs of our lemmas and theorem.

$$\begin{aligned} cr_\phi(A \cup B) &= cr_\phi(A) + cr_\phi(B) + cr_\phi(A, B) \\ cr_\phi(A, B \cup C) &= cr_\phi(A, B) + cr_\phi(A, C), \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where A , B and C are mutually disjoint subsets of E .

In the next section we shall give some lemmas, and then prove our theorem in the last one.

§2. Some Lemmas

Lemma 2.1 *Let G be a complete bipartite graph $K_{m,n}$ with the edge set E and the vertex bipartition (Y, Z) , where $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$, and $Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$. If ϕ is any good drawing of G , then*

$$(n-2)cr_\phi(E) = \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_i}).$$

Proof The conclusion follows from the fact that in the drawing of $K_{m,n}$, there are n drawings of $K_{m,n-1}$, and each crossing occurs in $(n-2)$ of them. \square

Lemma 2.2 *Let G be a complete tripartite graph $K_{s,m,n}$ with the edge set E and the vertex tripartition (X, Y, Z) , where $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_s\}$, $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$, and $Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$. If ϕ is any good drawing of G , then we have*

$$(i) \sum_{i=1}^n cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{z_i}) = (n-2)cr_{\phi}(E) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) + 2cr_{\phi}(E_{XY});$$

$$(ii) \sum_{i=1}^m cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_i}) = (m-2)cr_{\phi}(E) + \sum_{i=1}^m cr_{\phi}(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) + 2cr_{\phi}(E_{XZ})$$

Proof We only prove (i), because (ii) is analogous by the symmetry of the vertex tripartition of G . Using the formula (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} cr_{\phi}(E) &= cr_{\phi}(E_{XY} \cup E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \\ &= cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}) + cr_{\phi}(E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) + cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \\ &= cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}) + cr_{\phi}(E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Since $\langle E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ} \rangle$ is isomorphic to the complete bipartite graph $K_{s+m,n}$ with the vertex bipartition $(X \cup Y, Z)$, it follows from by Lemma 2.1 that

$$(n-2)cr_{\phi}(E_{XY} \cup E_{YZ}) = \sum_{i=1}^n cr_{\phi}((E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}) \quad (3)$$

On the other hand, using the formula (1) again we have

$$\begin{aligned} cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{z_i}) &= cr_{\phi}((E_{XY} \cup E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}) \\ &= cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}) + cr_{\phi}((E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}) \\ &\quad + cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, (E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}) \\ &= cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}) + cr_{\phi}((E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{j=1}^n cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, E_{z_j}) - cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}), \end{aligned}$$

namely, we have

$$cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{z_i}) = cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}) + cr_{\phi}((E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}) + \sum_{j=1}^n cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, E_{z_j}) - cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \quad (4)$$

Taking sum for i on the two sides of (4) above, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_i}) &= ncr_\phi(E_{XY}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi\left((E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}\right) \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_j}) - cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \right) \\
&= ncr_\phi(E_{XY}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi\left((E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \setminus E_{z_i}\right) + (n-1) \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \\
&= ncr_\phi(E_{XY}) + (n-2)cr_\phi(E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \\
&\quad + (n-1) \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \quad (\text{by (3) above}) \\
&= 2cr_\phi(E_{XY}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \\
&\quad + (n-2) \left(cr_\phi(E_{XZ}) + cr_\phi(E_{YZ}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \right) \\
&= 2cr_\phi(E_{XY}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) + (n-2)cr_\phi(E) \quad (\text{by (2) above})
\end{aligned}$$

This proves the lemma. \square

Note that in Lemma 2 above, if X is a set containing a single vertex x , then E_{XY} is the set of edges incident to x , and thus $cr_\phi(E_{XY}) = 0$ by any good drawing ϕ .

Lemma 2.3 *Let G be a complete tripartite graph $K_{1,5,n}$ with the edge set E and the vertex tripartition (X, Y, Z) , where $X = \{x\}$, $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_5\}$, and $Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$. If ϕ is a good drawing of G satisfying that $cr_\phi(E) = Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - a$ for some a . Then we have*

- (1) if $n = 2k$, then $\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \geq 2k^2 - 2k + 3a$;
- (2) if $n = 2k + 1$, then $\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \geq 2k^2 - 4 + 3a$.

Proof Let e_i denote the edge xy_i for $1 \leq i \leq 5$, and f_j denote the edge xz_j for $1 \leq j \leq n$. Without loss of generality, assume that under the drawing ϕ , the reverse clock order of these five edges e_i ($1 \leq i \leq 5$) around x is: $e_1 \rightarrow e_2 \rightarrow e_3 \rightarrow e_4 \rightarrow e_5$. These five edges form five angles: $\alpha_i = \angle e_i x e_{i+1}$, where $1 \leq i \leq 5$ and the indices are read module 5. We see that in the plane R^2 , there exists a circle neighbor $N(x, \varepsilon) = \{s \in R^2 : \|s - x\| < \varepsilon\}$, where ε is a sufficiently small positive number, such that for any other edge e of $K_{1,5,n}$ not incident with x , e can not be located in $N(x, \varepsilon)$. Since the graph $K_{1,5,n}$ has still n edges f_j that are incident to x ($1 \leq j \leq n$), let A_i denote the set of all those edges f_j , each of which lies in the angle α_i (see the Fig. 1 in the next page). Clearly, we have that $|A_1| + |A_2| + |A_3| + |A_4| = n$.

In the following, associated with the drawing ϕ of G , we shall produce five new graphs G_i , together with their respective good drawing ϕ_i ($1 \leq i \leq 5$), where each G_i is isomorphic to the complete bipartite graph $K_{5,n+1}$. We shall heavily illustrate how to obtain the graph G_1 and its drawing ϕ_1 , for the rest cases the method is analogous.

Fig. 1

First, we delete all edges in E_{y_1} and the vertex y_1 from G , and then remove the part of e_i lying in $N(x, \varepsilon)$ for $2 \leq i \leq 5$ (not remove the vertex x); add a new vertex z_{n+1} in some location of $e_4 \cap N(x, \varepsilon)$. Now we connected z_{n+1} to x and y_i ($i = 2, 3, 4, 5$) by the following way: connect z_{n+1} to x and y_4 respectively along the original two sections of e_4 ; connect z_{n+1} to y_3 by first traversing through α_3 (near to x) and then along the original section of e_3 lying out $N(x, \varepsilon)$; connect z_{n+1} to y_2 by successively traversing through α_3 and α_2 (near to x) and then along the original section of e_2 lying out $N(x, \varepsilon)$; connect z_{n+1} to y_5 by first traversing through α_4 (near to x) and then along the original section of e_5 lying out $N(x, \varepsilon)$. Then we obtain the graph G_1 with its a good drawing ϕ_1 . Obviously, G_1 is isomorphic to $K_{5,n+1}$. The following figure 2 helps us to understand the obtained graph G_1 and its drawing ϕ_1 , where the dotted line denote the way how z_{n+1} is connected to x and y_i ($2 \leq i \leq 5$).

Fig. 2

Then it is not difficult to see that

$$cr_{\phi_1}(G_1) = cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_1}) + |A_2| + 2|A_3| + |A_4|. \quad (4)$$

By the symmetry of y_i , we can analogously easily obtain the graphs G_i and its goods drawings ϕ_i for $2 \leq i \leq 5$. For example, the graph G_2 , together with its good drawing ϕ_2 , is displayed in

the following figure 3.

Fig. 3

Similarly, for ϕ_2, ϕ_3, ϕ_4 and ϕ_5 , we have respectively the following equalities :

$$cr_{\phi_2}(G_2) = cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_2}) + |A_3| + 2|A_4| + |A_5| \quad (5)$$

$$cr_{\phi_3}(G_3) = cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_3}) + |A_1| + 2|A_5| + |A_4| \quad (6)$$

$$cr_{\phi_4}(G_4) = cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_4}) + |A_2| + 2|A_1| + |A_5| \quad (7)$$

$$cr_{\phi_5}(G_5) = cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_5}) + |A_1| + 2|A_2| + |A_3| \quad (8)$$

Since each G_i ($1 \leq i \leq 5$) is isomorphic to the complete graph $K_{5,n+1}$, we get that $cr_{\phi_i}(G_i) \geq Z(5, n+1)$. Therefore, by (4)–(8) above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 5Z(5, n+1) &\leq \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_{\phi_i}(G_i) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_i}) + 4 \sum_{i=1}^5 |A_i| \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_{\phi}(E \setminus E_{y_i}) + 4n \\ &= 3cr_{\phi}(E) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_{\phi}(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) + 2cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}) + 4n \quad (\text{by Lemma ?? (2)}) \\ &= 3cr_{\phi}(E) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_{\phi}(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) + 4n \quad (\text{because } cr_{\phi}(E_{XY}) = 0) \end{aligned}$$

So it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) &\geq 5Z(5, n+1) - 3cr_\phi(E) - 4n \\
&= 5Z(5, n+1) - 3\left(Z(6, n) + 4\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - a\right) - 4n \\
&= \begin{cases} 2k^2 - 2k + 3a, & \text{when } n = 2k; \\ 2k^2 - 4 + 3a, & \text{when } n = 2k + 1 \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

This proves the lemma. \square

Lemma 2.4 *Let G be the complete tripartite graph $K_{1,5,n}$ with the edge set E and the vertex tripartition (X, Y, Z) , where $X = \{x\}$, $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_5\}$, and $Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$. Assume that $n = 2k + 1$, where $k \geq 0$. If ϕ is a good drawing of G satisfying that $cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_j}) = Z(6, n-1) + 4\left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \right\rfloor$ for any $1 \leq j \leq n$, then $cr_\phi(E) \neq Z(6, n) + 4\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1$.*

Proof Assume to contrary that $cr_\phi(E) = Z(6, n) + 4\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1$. By using the formula (2) in the proof of lemma 2.2, we have

$$Z(6, n) + 4\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1 = cr_\phi(E) = cr_\phi(E_{XZ}) + cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{YZ}) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}).$$

Since $\langle E_{XY} \cup E_{YZ} \rangle$ is isomorphic to the complete bipartite graph $K_{5, n+1}$, we have that $cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{YZ}) \geq Z(5, n+1)$. Noting that $cr_\phi(E_{XZ}) = 0$, we thus have

$$\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \leq Z(6, n) + 4\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1 - Z(5, n+1) = 2k^2 - 1$$

On the other hand, by our assumption that $cr_\phi(E) = Z(6, n) + 4\left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1$, and that $n = 2k + 1$, with the help of Lemma 2.3(ii) we have $\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \geq 2k^2 - 1$. This implies that

$$\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) = 2k^2 - 1 \tag{9}$$

Since $\langle E \setminus E_{z_j} \rangle$ is isomorphic to the complete tripartite graph $K_{1, m, n-1}$ with the vertex tripartition $(X, Y, Z \setminus \{z_j\})$, applying the formula (2) in the proof of Lemma 2.2 to the graph $\langle E \setminus E_{z_j} \rangle$, we have

$$cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_j}) = cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}) + cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{Y(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}),$$

where $E'_{y_i} = E_{X\{y_i\}} \cup E_{(Z \setminus \{z_j\})\{y_i\}}$.

Since $\langle E_{XY} \cup E_{Y(Z \setminus \{z_j\})} \rangle$ is isomorphic to the complete bipartite graph $K_{5, n}$, $cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{Y(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}) \geq Z(5, n)$. Again, since $E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}$ is the set of edges incident to x , we have that

$cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}) = 0$ by the good drawing ϕ . Therefore we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}) &= cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_j}) - cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}) - cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{Y(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}) \\
&= cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_j}) - cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{Y(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}) \\
&\leq Z(6, n-1) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \right\rfloor - Z(5, n) \\
&= 2k^2 - 2k
\end{aligned}$$

That is to say, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}) \leq 2k^2 - 2k \quad (10)$$

Because $E_{X\{z_j\}} \cup E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}$ is the set of edges incident to z_j , $cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) = 0$ by the good drawing ϕ . Note that $E'_{y_i} = E_{y_i} \setminus E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}$. Hence, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) &= cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E'_{y_i}) + cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \\
&= \left(cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}) + cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E'_{y_i}) \right) + cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \\
&= cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}) + cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{y_i} \setminus E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \\
&\quad + cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \\
&= cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}) + cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{y_i}) - cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \\
&\quad + cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) - cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \\
&= cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}) + cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{y_i}) + cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}})
\end{aligned}$$

Taking sum for i on two sides of the last equality above, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) &= \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{X(Z \setminus \{z_j\})}, E'_{y_i}) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{y_i}) \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}})
\end{aligned}$$

Combining with (9) and (10) above, we then obtain that

$$2k^2 - 1 \leq 2k^2 - 2k + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{y_i}) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \quad (11)$$

Again, taking sum for j on the two sides of the inequality (11) above, and noticing $n = 2k + 1$, we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{j=1}^n (2k^2 - 1) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^n (2k^2 - 2k) + \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{y_i}) + \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \\
&= (2k+1)(2k^2 - 2k) + \sum_{i=1}^5 \left(\sum_{j=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{X\{z_j\}}, E_{y_i}) \right) \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^5 \left(\sum_{j=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{\{z_j\}\{y_i\}}) \right) \\
&= (2k+1)(2k^2 - 2k) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{Z\{y_i\}}) \\
&= (2k+1)(2k^2 - 2k) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^5 \left(cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) - cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{X\{y_i\}}) \right) \quad (\text{because } E_{Z\{y_i\}} = E_{y_i} \setminus E_{X\{y_i\}}) \\
&= (2k+1)(2k^2 - 2k) + 2 \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \\
&\quad (\text{This is because } E_{XZ} \cup E_{X\{y_i\}} \text{ is the set of edges incident to } x, \text{ by the good} \\
&\quad \text{drawing } \phi, cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{Z\{y_i\}}) = 0 \text{ for any } 1 \leq i \leq 5) \\
&= (2k+1)(2k^2 - 2k) + 2(2k^2 - 1) \quad (\text{by (9) above})
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, it follows that $(2k+1)(2k-1) \leq 2(2k^2-1)$. This is a contradiction for any real number k , and proving the conclusion. \square

§3. Proof of Theorem 1

Let the complete tripartite graph $K_{1,5,n}$ having the edge set E and the vertex tripartition (X, Y, Z) , where $X = \{x\}$, $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_5\}$, and $Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$. To show that $cr(K_{1,5,n}) \leq Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$, we consider a drawing of $K_{1,5,n}$ as a immersion into R^2 , satisfying the following:

- (1) $\phi(x) = (0, 1)$;
- (2) $\phi(y_i) = (0, (-1)^i i)$, $i = 1, 2$, $\phi(y_3) = (\varepsilon, -2)$, $\phi(y_4) = (\varepsilon, 3)$, $\phi(y_5) = (2\varepsilon, 4)$, where ε is a sufficiently small positive;
- (3) $\phi(z_j) = ((-1)^j \lfloor \frac{j+1}{2} \rfloor, 0)$.

For example, a drawing of $K_{1,5,5}$ on the plane is shown in the Fig.4. It is not difficult to see that $cr_\phi(E) = Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. This thus shows that $cr(K_{1,5,n}) \leq Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. In order to prove the theorem, we only need to prove the conclusion that $cr_\phi(K_{1,5,n}) \geq Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for any good drawing ϕ . Assume to contrary that there is a good drawing ϕ of $K_{1,5,n}$ satisfying $cr_\phi(K_{1,5,n}) = Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - a$, where $a \geq 1$. We now consider the following two cases, according to as n is even or odd.

Claim 1 *The desired conclusion is true when $n (= 2k)$ is even.*

Subproof By our assumption that $cr_\phi(K_{1,5,n}) = Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - a$, it then follows from Lemma 2.3(i) that

$$\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{xz}, E_{y_i}) \geq 2k^2 - 2k + 3a.$$

Fig. 4

Note that $cr_\phi(E_{XZ}) = 0$ by the good drawing ϕ . Since $\langle E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ} \rangle$ is isomorphic to the complete bipartite graph $K_{5,n+1}$ with the vertex bipartition $(Y, X \cup Z)$, we have that $cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{YZ}) \geq Z(5, n+1)$. Using the formulas (2) in the proof of Lemma 2.2, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} Z(6, n) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - a &= cr_\phi(E) \\ &= cr_\phi(E_{XZ}) + cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{YZ}) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \\ &\geq Z(5, n+1) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \leq 2k^2 - 2k - a$. So, we get that $2k^2 - 2k + 3a \leq 2k^2 - 2k - a$, namely, $a \leq 0$. This contradicts to the hypothesis that $a \geq 1$, proving the claim.

Claim 2 *The desired conclusion is true when $n (= 2k + 1)$ is odd.*

Subproof. Since n is odd, by Lemma 2.3(ii) we first have

$$\sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \geq 2k^2 - 4 + 3a$$

Similarly, using the formulas (2) in the proof of Lemma 2.2, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} Z(6, n) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - a &= cr_\phi(E) \\ &\geq Z(5, n+1) + \sum_{i=1}^5 cr_\phi(E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}), \end{aligned}$$

which follows that $\sum_{i=1}^5 (E_{XZ}, E_{y_i}) \leq 2k^2 - a$. Hence, we get that $2k^2 - 4 + 3a \leq 2k^2 - a$, namely $a \leq 1$. Since $a \geq 1$ by our assumption, this implies that $a = 1$, and thus it must be that

$$cr_\phi(E) = Z(6, n) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1 \quad (12)$$

Again, with the help of the formula (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} cr_\phi(E) &= cr_\phi(E_{XY} \cup E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \\ &= cr_\phi(E_{XY}) + cr_\phi(E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) + cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \\ &= cr_\phi(E_{XY}) + cr_\phi(E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\langle E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ} \rangle$ is isomorphic to the complete bipartite graph $K_{6,n}$ with the vertex bipartition $(X \cup Y, Z)$, it has that $cr_\phi(E_{XZ} \cup E_{YZ}) \geq Z(6, n)$. Noting that $cr_\phi(E_{XY}) = 0$ by the good drawing of ϕ , we thus have

$$Z(6, n) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1 = cr_\phi(E) \geq Z(6, n) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}),$$

which follows that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_i}) \leq Z(6, n) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1 - Z(6, n) = 4k - 1 \quad (13)$$

Combining with Lemma 2.2(i), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_i}) &= 2cr_\phi(E_{XY}) + \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_j}) + (n-2)cr_\phi(E) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E_{XY}, E_{z_j}) + (n-2)cr_\phi(E) \quad (\text{because } cr_\phi(E_{XY}) = 0) \\ &\leq 4k - 1 + (n-2) \left(Z(6, n) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor - 1 \right) \quad (\text{by (12) and (13) above}) \\ &= n \left(Z(6, n-1) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) \quad (\text{because } n = 2k + 1) \end{aligned}$$

That is to say, we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^n cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_i}) \leq n \left(Z(6, n-1) + 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \right\rfloor \right) \quad (14)$$

On the other hand, since, for any $1 \leq i \leq n$, $\langle E \setminus E(z_i) \rangle$ is isomorphic to the complete tripartite graph $K_{1,5,n-1}$, and since $n-1$ is even, it follows from the truth of Claim 1 that $cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_i}) \geq Z(6, n-1) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$ for any $1 \leq i \leq n$. Combined with (14) above, it must happen that $cr_\phi(E \setminus E_{z_i}) = Z(6, n-1) + 4 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$ for any $1 \leq i \leq n$. This, together with n being odd and (12) above, contradicts Lemma 2.4, proving this claim.

Therefore, the proof of Theorem 1 is finished. \square

References

- [1] Kouchei Asano, The crossing number of $K_{1,3,n}$ and $k_{2,3,n}$, *J.Graph Theory*, **10** (1980), 1-8.
- [2] A.M.Dean and R.B.Richter, The crossing number of $C_4 \times C_4$, *J.Graph Theory*, **19** (1995), 125-129.
- [3] P.Erdős and R.K.Guy, Crossing number problems, *Am.Math.Month*, **80** (1973), 52-58.
- [4] M.R.Garey and D.S.Johnson, Crossing number is NP-complete, *SIAM J.Algebraic.Discrete Methods*, **4** (1983), 312-316.
- [5] Yuanqiu Huang, The crossing number of $K_{1,4,n}$, *Discrete Mathematics*(to appear).
- [6] Stanislav Jendrol and Marián Klešč, On the graphs whose line graphs have crossing number one , *J. Graph Theory*, **37** (2001), 181-188.
- [7] D.J.Kleitman, The crossing number of $K_{5,n}$, *J.Combinatorial Theory*, **9** (1970) 315-323.
- [8] L.F.Mao, An introduction to Smarandache multi-spaces and mathematical combinatorics, *Scientia Magna*, Vol.3, No.1(2007), 54-80.
- [9] Marián Klešč, The crossing numbers of products of path ans stars with 4-vertex graphs,*J. Graph Theory*, **18**(6) (1994), 605-614.
- [10] V.R.Kulli, D.G.Akka and L.W.Beineke, On the line graphs with crossing number 1, *J. Graph Theory*, **3** (1979), 87-90.
- [11] Marián Klešč,R.Bruce Richter and Ian Stobert, The crossing number of $C_5 \times C_n$, *J.Graph Theory*, **22**(3) (1996), 239-243.
- [12] Dan McQuillan and R.Bruce Richter, On the crossing numbers of certain generalized peterson graphs, *Discrete Math.*, **104** (1992), 311-320.
- [13] R.Bruce Richter and Gelasio Salazar, The crossing number of $C_6 \times C_n$, *Australasian J.of Combinatorics*, **23** (2001), 135-143.
- [14] R.B.Richter and C.Thomassen, Intersection of curve systems and the crossing number of $C_5 \times C_5$,*Discrete Comp.Geom.*, **13**(1995), 149-159.
- [15] D.R.Woodall, Cyclic-order graphs and Zarankiewicz's crossing number conjecture *J.Graph Theory*, **17**(1993), 657-671.